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Lower Bounds for Covering Codes in
Rosenbloom-Tsfasman Spaces

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Abstract

In this work, the sphere covering bound on covering codes in Rosenbloom-Tsfasman spaces (RT spaces) is improved by generalizing the excess counting method.

1 Introduction

Let $K_q(m, R)$ be the smallest cardinality of a q -ary code of length m and covering radius R . The computation of $K_q(m, R)$ has been a great challenge in coding theory since the seminal papers [2] and [8]. We refer to the book [5] for an overview on the topic.

The most natural lower bound on $K_q(m, R)$ is called the sphere covering bound. Significant techniques have been developed to improve this bound. In particular, the first ideas of the so-called excess counting method are due to [6], rediscovered later by [9, 10] and investigated by [4].

Rosenbloom and Tsfasman [7] introduced a metric nowadays known as RT metric or NRT metric, which generalizes the Hamming metric. In particular, covering codes in RT spaces induced by a chain are determined by [1] in connection with perfect codes and are mentioned as a function by [11]. An extension to an arbitrary RT space is proposed by [3].

Let $K_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ denote the minimal number of codewords of a covering code with radius R in the RT space \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} . The knowledge about lower bounds for $K_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ is scarce due to the difficulty of improving the sphere covering bound. The following question arises naturally: how to extend the excess counting method to covering codes in RT spaces? As the main goal of this work, we attempt to answer this question.

2 RT metric and covering codes

We now review the RT metric according to the approach in [1] and [3]. Let P be a finite partial ordered set (poset) and denote its partial order relation by \preceq . A poset is a *chain* when any two elements are comparable; a poset is an *anti-chain* when no two distinct elements are comparable.

A subset I of P is an *ideal* of P when the following property holds: if $b \in I$ and $a \preceq b$, then $a \in I$. The *ideal generated* by a subset A of P is the ideal of the smallest cardinality which contains A , denoted by $\langle A \rangle$.

Let m and s be positive integers. Consider the set $[m \times s] := \{1, \dots, ms\}$ partitioned into m pairwise disjoint subsets $\{(i-1)s+1, \dots, is\}$ of size s , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. Each one of these parts is a chain whose elements are ordered as $(i-1)s+1 \preceq \dots \preceq is$. Hence the set $[m \times s]$ has the structure of a poset: it is the union of m disjoint chains with s elements each, which is known as the *Rosenbloom-Tsfasman poset* $[m \times s]$, or briefly, the RT poset $[m \times s]$.

The *RT distance* between x and y in \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} is defined as

$$d_{RT}(x, y) = |\langle \text{supp}(x - y) \rangle| = |\langle \{i : x_i \neq y_i\} \rangle|.$$

The set \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} endowed with the RT distance is called a *Rosenbloom-Tsfasman space*, or simply, an *RT space*. The RT sphere centered at x of radius R is the set $B_q^{RT}(x, R) = \{y \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} : d_{RT}(x, y) \leq R\}$, and its cardinality is denoted by $V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$.

Given an RT poset $[m \times s]$, let C be a subset of \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} . The code C is an *R-covering* of the RT space \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} when satisfies the property: for every $x \in \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms}$ there is a codeword $c \in C$ such that $d_{RT}(x, c) \leq R$. The number $K_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ denotes the smallest cardinality of an *R-covering* of the RT space \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} .

The sphere covering bound for $K_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ is $\frac{q^{ms}}{V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)}$. The sphere covering bound for $R = 1$ in a Hamming space (when $s = 1$) yields $K_q(m, 1) \geq \frac{q^m}{(q-1)^{m+1}}$. An important improvement of this lower bound is stated below.

Theorem 1. ([6]; [10]) *If m and q are even, then $K_q(m, 1) \geq \frac{q^m}{(q-1)^m}$.*

For $m = 2^n$ and $q = 2$, the lower bound given by Theorem 1 is the exact value for $K_2(2^n, 1)$, a rare phenomenon in the literature.

Corollary 2. ([6]; [9]) *For any positive integer n , $K_2(2^n, 1) = 2^{2^n - n}$.*

3 The parity of $V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ and intersection numbers

We connect the parity of $V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ with the parity of the binomial coefficients under some conditions on the parameters.

Proposition 3. *Let q be an even positive integer.*

1. *If $m \leq R \leq s$, then $V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ is even.*
2. *If $R \leq s < m$, then $V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ is odd if and only if $\binom{m-1}{R}$ is odd. In particular, $V_2^{RT}(m, s, s)$ is odd if and only if $\binom{m-1}{s}$ is odd.*

Inspired by applications of the intersection numbers in Hamming spaces by [4] and [9], we extend these numbers to a general RT space. Let $\mathbf{0}$ denote the zero vector in \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} . Given an arbitrary x in \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} and R such that $0 \leq R \leq ms$, the *intersection number* is defined as

$$\Gamma(\mathbb{Z}_q^{ms}, x, R) := |B^{RT}(x, R) \cap B^{RT}(\mathbf{0}, R)|.$$

Proposition 4. *1. Let x be a nonzero vector of \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} . If q is even, then $\Gamma(\mathbb{Z}_q^{ms}, x, 1)$ is even.*

2. *For any nonzero vector x in \mathbb{Z}_2^{ms} and for any $R \geq 1$, the number $\Gamma(\mathbb{Z}_2^{ms}, x, R)$ is even.*

4 The excess bound for RT spaces

We generalize the excess counting method for RT spaces.

Theorem 5. *(The excess bound for RT space) Let C be an R -covering of the RT space \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} and let $\bar{C} = \mathbb{Z}_q^{ms} \setminus C$ be its complement. Suppose that*

1. *$V_q^{RT}(m, s, R)$ is odd;*
2. *for each $x \in \bar{C}$ and for each $c \in C$, $\Gamma(\mathbb{Z}_q^{ms}, x - c, R)$ is even.*

Then $K_q^{RT}(m, s, R) \geq \frac{q^{ms}}{V_q^{RT}(m, s, R) - 1}$.

We remark that the excess bound always improves the sphere covering bound.

Corollary 6. *For m and q be even integers, $K_q^{RT}(m, s, 1) \geq \frac{q^{ms}}{(q-1)m}$.*

Proof. Since m is even, the number $V_q^{RT}(m, s, 1) = 1 + (q-1)m$ is odd. Proposition 4 part (1) states that $\Gamma(\mathbb{Z}_q^{ms}, x - c, 1)$ is even, since q is even. Theorem 5 provides the bound desired. \square

Corollary 6 extends Theorem 1. It is worth mentioning that Theorem 1 requires information on the parity of $V_q^{RT}(m, s, 1) = 1 + (q - 1)m$, a simple case when compared with the most complicated and general situation in RT spaces, stated in Theorem 5. Moreover, the previous bound is sharp at least for an infinite class of parameters, generalizing Corollary 2.

Corollary 7. For any positive integers n and s , $K_2^{RT}(2^n, s, 1) = 2^{2^n s - n}$.

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